

Chromatin-Driven Behavior of Topologically Associating Domains

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Abstract

Metazoan genomes are highly organized inside the cell nucleus. Topologically associating domains (TADs) represent the building blocks of genome organization, but their linear modularity does not explain alone their spatial organization. Indeed, the chromatin type adorning a TAD can shape its structure and drives its nuclear positioning and its function. Genome-wide association studies revealed mainly four chromatin types: active chromatin, Polycomb-repressed chromatin, null chromatin and constitutive heterochromatin. In this review, we will describe the main three-dimensional features of each chromatin type and finally their relationships with TAD organization and epigenetic memory

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Introduction

Chromatin fiber is not randomly distributed inside the cell nucleus. Firstly, chromosomes are confined in discrete “territories” [1,2], and within them, further levels of spatial organization are imposed to chromatin. Metazoan genomes share a modular organization of their chromatin in structures called “topologically associating domains” (TADs). TADs can be defined as linear units of chromatin that fold as discrete three-dimensional (3D) structures tending to favor internal, rather than external, chromatin interactions. They are delimited by sharp boundaries, which contain housekeeping genes and insulator sites. TADs are detected by methods such as Hi-C [1,2], which allows genome-wide identification of chromatin contacts [3–5], and they correspond to chromosomal domains, previously identified by microscopy [6]. Remarkably, TADs are conserved among different cell types in animals, whereas they have not been detected in plants and yeasts [7–11], demonstrating that alternative modes of genome folding are possible. Besides their 3D organization, metazoan genomes are organized in linear clusters of co-expressed genes [12], although there is a certain degree of liberty in expression within gene clusters [13,14]. These co-expression clusters span on average about 100 kb in *Drosophila melanogaster* [15]

and 1 Mb in humans [13]. Strikingly, these genomic ranges correspond to the average TAD sizes in both species.

The investigation of chromatin landscapes in *metazoa* through genome-wide association studies proved to be a fruitful approach [3,16–23]. In these studies, the presence of several chromatin factors and histone modifications were analyzed and finally combined, in order to obtain a global overview of the chromatin landscape. Theoretically, a huge number of chromatin type combinations were possible but, in fact, a very limited number of these were shown to cover the vast majority of the genome. The precise number of chromatin types varied among the studies, according to the algorithm used, the resolution and other parameters. Despite these technical differences, every report basically recapitulated the presence of an active chromatin environment, sometimes further subdivided, and three major types of repressive chromatin: a Polycomb-repressed environment, a null environment and a heterochromatic environment.

Strikingly, TADs were found to overlap with linear chromatin domains [3–5,24,25]; therefore, a defined chromatin type can be assigned to every single TAD. Consequently, the chromatin flavor of a given TAD can define its functional identity and drive its 3D organization. Moreover, the chromatin identity of a given TAD can guide its nuclear positioning and

therefore shape the genome architecture. Although TAD borders are generally not variable among different cell types, chromatin states can change dramatically their identity. The chromatin coating the genome of a given species can be reshaped in different cell types and conditions, hence reflecting its activity [26]. The conserved modularity of TAD organization can be combined with the variable nature of chromatin identity. In this review, we will recapitulate the current understanding about the 3D organization of the abovementioned chromatin types. Recent and older studies concerning the chromatin compaction, local interactions, long-range interactions and the nuclear positioning of each chromatin type will be reviewed. These studies have been conducted using a plethora of different methodologies, spanning from microscopy-based to cell-population approaches. We invite readers to refer to recent reviews on the technical aspects of these approaches [27–29]. Based on this multi-tiered evidence, a nuclear architecture model based on TADs and their chromatin types will be proposed.

Active Chromatin

Active chromatin is here referred as the fraction of chromatin that is in a competent state for gene expression and initiating DNA replication. Different cell types are characterized by specific sets of active and silenced genes. The specific portion of active chromatin residing in the nucleus of a given cell type reflects its identity [26]. Active chromatin is the most heterogeneous chromatin type, since it displays binding sites for many chromatin factors and it is adorned by a plethora of histone modifications as H3 methylations on lysine 4, lysine 36 and lysine 79 and acetylation of multiple lysines on H3 and H4 N-terminal tails [17,23]. The deposition of such marks reflects the identity of the underlying functional element (e.g., promoter, gene body, enhancer, etc.) and its degree of activity (e.g., active, poised, etc.). Several chromatin factors often work cooperatively and the surrounding chromatin environment can alter their binding [23]. Finally, the specific characteristics of a gene (e.g., length, presence of introns, etc.) or a promoter (e.g., housekeeping, developmentally regulated, etc.) can influence the local chromatin features as nucleosome positioning, binding of specific factors and deposition of histone modifications [17,30].

Active chromatin represents a highly accessible environment, displaying an increased density of DNase I hypersensitive sites when compared to other types of chromatin [31]. In *D. melanogaster*, active chromatin domains show a more rapid decay in contacts frequency as a function of genomic distance than other domain types, revealing a decondensed organization [3]. Genome-wide association studies confirmed the extensive heterogeneity and the higher

accessibility of active chromatin. Depending on the algorithm used to categorize the different chromatin types, some studies grouped active chromatin as a single chromatin variety [3,20,21], whereas other studies identified subpatterns, characterizing elements such as promoters, gene bodies, active introns, enhancers and so on [16,18,19,22]. Finer classifications can uncover chromatin patterns that are specific for housekeeping genes and tissue-specific genes [23] or X-linked genes [17].

Active chromatin is organized in linear domains, on average, shorter than other chromatin types. Those domains cluster groups of active genes, which regulation relies on distal regulatory elements placed inside megabase-sized domains [24,32,33]. Active domains can be organized in TADs [3,4,34,35], suggesting that these clusters of active genes are spatially independent from nearby domains.

3D organization of active TADs

The chromatin fiber forming active TADs does not fold randomly but is highly organized in the 3D space. Although chromatin contacts are not random, they are quite variable between two cells [36]. The internal interaction profile is even more different between cells of a different type [5,37]. At the single gene level, promoters display preferential interactions with their downstream gene bodies rather than with upstream sequences [37–39]. This asymmetric distribution is independent of ongoing transcription [37]. Furthermore, some genes can form a promoter–terminator loop, which formation does not seem to be strictly dependent on the gene activity and its functional relevance has still to be elucidated [40,41]. In addition, promoters of coregulated genes often contact one another [38,39].

A typical metazoan gene has a complex regulatory network, which includes the presence of distal regulatory elements called enhancers. Although several models to explain the functional relation between enhancers and promoters were originally proposed, it is now accepted that enhancers work through a physical interaction with the promoter, therefore forming a chromatin loop [42–44]. Enhancer function is usually independent on orientation and distance to the target promoter [45] and can be located upstream, downstream or in intronic regions [30]. These interactions are mediated by both specific and general transcription factors such as the mediator complex, cohesins and CTCF [46–48]. Promoter–enhancer interaction networks are highly dependent on the nature of the gene. For instance, promoters of many housekeeping genes seem to have no enhancer [37] although this result might be affected by resolution issues, whereas promoters regulated by a single enhancer are usually controlling tissue-specific genes [49]. This kind of enhancers tends to be in close proximity to the promoter [50]. Alternatively, several enhancers can regulate a single promoter [51], usually

Fig. 1. Specific but variable interactions inside TADs. (a) Enhancer–promoter interactions occurring in an active TAD are represented. In the cell type “X”, the enhancer 3 binds the promoter 1 despite that it is not the closest promoter linearly. The promoter 2 is active without being in contact with any enhancer. Despite the fact that enhancer 1 binds the promoter 3, it is not transcriptionally active yet. In the cell type “Y”, the promoter 1 is bound by the enhancer 2 and not by the enhancer 3 anymore. The enhancer 1 switches its contacts from the promoter 3 and the promoter 4. (b) PRE–promoter interactions occurring in Polycomb-repressed TADs are represented. In the cell type “X”, a PRE contacts four promoters, causing the silencing of their downstream genes. In the cell type “Y”, the contacts between the promoter 1 and the PRE are lost, whereas the other promoters are still bound to the PRE. This release causes a looping-out of the chromatin associated with the gene 1 and concomitantly its transcriptional derepression.

controlling broadly expressed genes. In this case, different subsets of enhancers are active on their target gene in different cell types, revealing high cell-type specificity in promoter–enhancer interactions [24,38,39,52]. On the other hand, single enhancers can control several genes [37,53], which are usually coregulated. Finally, the association between an enhancer and its target promoter is not guided just by linear proximity, since most of the enhancers control promoters located beyond the nearest gene [39,52] (Fig. 1a). These association rules are in part driven by the presence of insulator sequences, which can form DNA loops through insulator binding proteins. In mammals, CTCF dimers mediate these DNA looping, whereas other organisms as *D. melanogaster* exhibit a more diverse set of insulator binding proteins

[54]. Interestingly in a human fibroblast cell line, it was observed that enhancer–promoter looping is already preset before gene activation, since the stimulation of a set of inducible genes did not result in any consistent spatial reorganization [37]. A similar mechanism has been recently observed in *D. melanogaster* embryos. Here, promoter–enhancer interactions are very conserved between different developmental stages and they are often associated with paused RNA Pol II, arising before gene activation [55].

Long-range interactions and nuclear positioning of active TADs

Even though internal interactions are highly preferred, interactions between active loci located on

different TADs can occur [3,36]. Furthermore, specific interactions can involve loci on different chromosomes, and in some cases, they may have functional significance [56]. The existence of inter-chromosomal interactions between active domains was further confirmed by genome-wide studies [39,52]. The role of the insulator protein CTCF for these interactions appears to be crucial. In *D. melanogaster*, it was demonstrated that CTCF could promote long-range interactions of distant transgenes, whereas enhancer presence could only increase their colocalization [57].

Besides specific cases of regulation *in trans*, long-range interactions between active regions can have a strong impact on genome organization. Indeed, clustering of linearly distant RNA Pol II genes was observed in specific cases [43,58]. For example, coregulated genes sharing the same transcription factors or involved in the same pathways can colocalize when they are transcribed in the same moment [59–62]. Their colocalization frequencies are higher than with other transcribed genes, suggesting the presence of specialized factories dedicated to their transcription [58]. Transcription factories are described as proteinaceous structures transcribing several RNA Pol II genes and characterized by an average diameter of 130 nm in erythroid cells [63]. RNA Pol II activity is higher at the external surface of these structures [64], which form upon induction of transcription [65] by specific transcription factors [62]. In this context, long-range interactions could favor coregulation of distant genes by increasing the local amount of factors required for their transcription. These findings are consistent with a conserved tendency of active chromatin domains to interact specifically with other active domains, even when placed on other chromosomes. In contrast, other chromatin types are less prone to interact with other chromosomes [3,36,66,67].

A special case of transcription factory is the nucleolus, the largest compartment in the nucleus. Nucleoli are the places where rRNA is synthesized, accounting for up to 80% of the total RNA amount in a cell. In these compartments, rRNA is also processed and finally assembled with ribosomal proteins. Arrays of rRNA genes are arranged in several nucleolus organizer regions, which can be located in the same or in different chromosomes, depending on the species. These regions are not all active in every cell, but the active ones cluster together to form one to several nucleoli [68]. Their clustering is likely to be dependent on the essential transcription factor UBF, which does not bind the inactive nucleolus organizer regions [69]. Furthermore, active rRNA genes can form loops between promoter and terminator, enabling coordination of their expression [70].

Compartmentalization of the active chromatin was already observed in Hi-C studies as a spatial segregation from inactive chromatin [2]. Active chromatin is positioned preferentially in the nuclear interior [71,72].

This tendency is reflected at the chromosome scale, as gene-dense and more active chromosomes reside in a more internal position than gene-poor and silent ones [73]. An intriguing hypothesis is that, when several TADs are in an active state on a given chromosome, contacts between transcriptional complexes at active chromatin may cooperatively bring the chromosome toward a more internal position. In contrast, a chromosome depleted in active TADs would be relegated to a more peripheral location. The driving forces bringing the active TADs toward the center of the nucleus could be the transcriptional factories, which in a cell-specific way might bring together different active TADs. Alternatively, the internal positioning of active chromatin could be due to a passive force, resulting in preferential positioning of the null TADs to the nuclear periphery. These two hypotheses do not necessarily exclude each other and further investigation will be needed to better elucidate this point.

In conclusion, active chromatin can be described as a heterogeneous environment, highly accessible and decondensed. 3D interactions inside active TADs are specific and crucial for gene expression although variable at single cell level. The vast majority of those interactions occur within each active TAD, but inter-TAD interactions, especially among coregulated genes, are possible. Active TADs are placed preferentially in the inner part of the nucleus and have preferential contact with other active TADs, rather than inactive ones.

Polycomb-Repressed Chromatin

Polycomb group genes (PcG) were firstly identified in *D. melanogaster* as repressors of Hox genes [74]. Later, PcG proteins were found to be organized in mainly two multiprotein complexes, that is, Polycomb repressive complexes 1 and 2 (PRC1 and PRC2), which can respectively ubiquitylate H2AK119 and monomethylate, dimethylate and trimethylate H3K27 [75,76]. Finally, genome-wide studies revealed that PcG proteins are widespread transcriptional repressors, which are responsible for the silencing of a portion of metazoan genomes [77–79]. PRC1 and PRC2 lack DNA binding motifs; therefore, they have to be recruited by specific DNA-binding factors [80]. In *D. melanogaster*, these recruiters drive PRC1 and PRC2 to specific Polycomb responsive elements (PREs) [81]. Genomic regions containing arrays of PREs form large domains covered by the H3K27me3 mark. The most studied examples are the two homeotic complexes, that is, Antennapedia complex and Bithorax complex (ANT-C and BX-C), located on chromosome arm 3R. In mammals, Polycomb-bound regions are found mainly on Hox clusters, X-inactivation sites, imprinted regions and thousands of genes bearing CpG islands [82]. As expected, Polycomb-repressed

chromatin emerged as a distinct chromatin type in all the genome-wide studies aimed to identify chromatin domains in *metazoa* [3,16–23]. PcG proteins and H3K27me3 demarcate a significant portion of the *D. melanogaster* genome, which shows very low transcriptional activity and late replication timing [3,17,23]. Similar scenarios were observed in mammals [16,18,19,21] and *Caenorhabditis elegans* [22], demonstrating that this silencing strategy is evolutionary conserved.

In *D. melanogaster*, Polycomb-repressed domains correspond to a subset of TADs [3], linking their functional specificity with an independent spatial organization. The situation appears to be more complex in mammalian genomes. Here, the correspondence between Polycomb-repressed chromatin and specific TADs is not as straightforward. This is due to only a partial overlap in lengths' ranges between TADs (100 kb to 10 Mb) and H3K27me3 domains (1 kb to 100 kb) [83]. One explanation for this discrepancy might be the different resolution between fly and mammalian Hi-C studies. Since mammalian genomes are 10- to 20-fold larger than in flies, a sequencing depth of 100- to 400-fold would be required in order to reach the same resolution in contact mapping. Lacking this sequencing depth, it is possible that part of the TAD boundaries may have been missed in currently available maps. However, cases of H3K27me3-specific TADs have been reported on the inactive X chromosome [4] and on Hox clusters [34,35], suggesting that, at least in some cases, this correspondence can be similar to what was observed in *D. melanogaster*. Moreover, clusters of single Polycomb-repressed genes that do not form large and uniform H3K27me3 domains could in principle reside inside the same TAD and may form higher-order 3D structures that could be seen as "Polycomb-repressed TADs".

Polycomb-repressed TAD compaction

While initial studies assessing accessibility to nucleases failed to detect Polycomb chromatin compaction [84], later reports showed that chromatin bound by PcG proteins has a reduced accessibility when compared to euchromatin [85–87], suggesting the presence of higher-order structures comparable with classic heterochromatin [85]. Fitzgerald *et al.* obtained similar results while testing the accessibility of the BX-C. They observed that GAL-4-dependent activation of RNA Pol II transcription and FLP-mediated recombination are specifically suppressed in the Polycomb-repressed segments, while transcription by the less bulky T7 RNAP is only partially blocked in a subset of PcG-repressed cells. This behavior was dependent on the presence of PcG proteins [88].

Several lines of evidences indicate that the major responsible for chromatin compaction is PRC1. PRC1

can compact nucleosomal arrays *in vitro*, independently of the presence of histone tails. This compaction is dependent on nucleosomes, rather than on linker DNA, with templates organized in a ratio of one PRC1 every three nucleosomes [89]. In *D. melanogaster*, the C-terminal region of the PRC1 subunit Psc plays a central role in this process [89,90]. Moreover, the presence of Psc mutant alleles alters PRC1 activity *in vitro* [90]. In mouse, however, a Polycomb ortholog called CBX2 is the main responsible for *in vitro* chromatin compaction [91]. The common feature shared by the *D. melanogaster* Psc and the mouse CBX2 is an unstructured highly basic domain, which firstly interacts with a single nucleosome, then tethers more nucleosomes together and finally promotes oligomerization through the formation of higher-order structures [91]. Ph, another PRC1 member, promotes oligomerization via its SAM domain, facilitating PRC1 and PRC2 binding and fostering chromatin compaction [92]. The lack of RING1B, the catalytic subunit of PRC1, is responsible for chromatin decompaction on HoxB and HoxD loci in mouse ESCs. This effect is not just a consequence of transcriptional induction and it is independent of its ubiquityltransferase activity [93]. RING1B is responsible for chromatin compaction also at Kcnq1 imprinted locus in mouse. This locus shows a 3D contracted state that differs from the maternal allele when paternally imprinted [94]. The authors conclude that RING1B is responsible for genomic contraction *in vivo*. Interestingly, they found that EZH2, the catalytic subunit of PRC2, also plays a role in this process independently on PRC1. Furthermore, a PRC2 complex containing EZH1 can compact chromatin independently on its enzymatic activity [95]. Finally, indications for a cooperative function between PRC1 and PRC2 suggest that the PRC1-mediated compaction could be facilitated by the PRC2 activity and *vice versa*. Indeed, reconstituted *D. melanogaster* PRC2 exhibits improved activity on dense rather than dispersed oligonucleosomes, indicating that chromatin, when compacted by PRC1, is a more suitable substrate to exert PRC2 function [96].

3D organization of Polycomb-repressed TADs

A complex issue is to determine how chromatin is organized 3D inside these compact domains. Pioneering studies shed light on the spatial organization of the Bithorax complex in *D. melanogaster*. The *Fab-7* PRE and the *Abd-B* promoter were found to interact specifically, although they are distant 35 kb. These interactions occur in nuclei where the gene is silenced by PcG proteins and they are dependent by the presence of a boundary element of the *Fab-7* region [97]. In 2007, Lanzaolo *et al.* suggested that the BX-C forms a topologically independent structure. When repressed by PcG proteins, the BX-C is organized in a multi-loop structure where specific interactions occur among PREs, promoters and 3' end of the genes,

Fig. 2. Linear representation of TADs and their variations between cell types. (a) The cell type “X” displays two null TADs depicted in black (TAD1 and TAD2), harboring mainly inactive genes. In the cell type “Y”, the TAD 2 is completely switched into an active TAD, depicted in red, whose genes are now mostly active. The TAD borders are fixed between the two cell types. (b) An active TAD (TAD1) and a Polycomb-repressed TAD (TAD2) are depicted in red and blue, respectively. In some instances, TAD borders can shift between different cell types. Indeed, in cell type “Y”, the active TAD1 incorporates one gene that was part of the TAD2 in the cell type “X”.

forming three subdomains corresponding to the three transcriptional units. When one of those transcriptional units is expressed, the PRE dedicated to its regulation loses most of its interactions within rest of the domain, particularly with its proximal promoter, suggesting a looping-out of the active gene [98]. These specific interactions inside the BX-C can also occur *in trans*, connecting regulatory sequences of homologous chromosomes [99]. Moreover, the presence of an insulator can block PRE–promoter contacts and interfere with gene silencing in a transgenic construct [100] (Fig. 1b).

3D organization of Hox genes was also studied in mammals. Mammalian genomes bear four Hox clusters that have evolved by duplication events from a common ancestor [101]. They are organized in multi-loop structures, preferentially interacting within the domain, even though external interactions can be observed at lower frequencies [34,35,102,103], as in their *D. melanogaster* counterpart [66,67]. Repression of groups of genes inside these clusters correlates with chromatin condensation and H3K27me3 enrichment [103], whereas transcriptional activation results in decreased interaction frequencies and loss of H3K27me3 [104]. Interestingly, transcriptional induction leads to the disruption of these looping contacts, not only at the induced genes but also in the whole HoxA cluster [102]. It was proposed that EZH2 might not be responsible for the DNA looping, whereas CTCF represents a good candidate for the looping function [102,104]. When a Hox cluster is completely repressed, it is covered with the H3K27me3 mark and it is organized in a single 3D compartment. On the other hand, when a portion of the cluster is transcrip-

tionally active, a bimodal 3D organization appears, mirroring the underlying chromatin profiles. In other words, the linear epigenetic boundary reflects the spatial organization of two separated 3D compartments, a repressed one and an active one. Strikingly, when the expression profile changes, the TAD boundary shifts concomitantly [34,35]. These findings demonstrate that, at least in some cases, the boundary between two TADs can move linearly, according to the underlying chromatin environment (Fig. 2b). Outside Hox clusters, multi-looped conformations can be found in other PcG-repressed loci in human and mouse, such as the GATA-4 locus [105], the INK4-ARF locus [106] and the Meis2 locus [107]. In each case, transcription has a disruptive role on these interactions and Polycomb components are involved in their maintenance.

Polycomb-repressed TAD long-range interactions and nuclear positioning

In addition to intra-TAD contacts [3,34,66,67,98], Polycomb-repressed TADs show long-range interactions. Two studies used a 4C strategy in *D. melanogaster* with baits within the BX-C. Long-range interactions involved other Polycomb-bound domains placed from the same chromosome [66,67]. Larger Polycomb-repressed TADs having more PREs interact more often [67]. Moreover, long-range interactions are evolutionary conserved despite the fact that genomic rearrangements make the linear arrangement of the underlying chromosomes substantially different [66]. Earlier reports stated that long-range interactions, even across different chromosomes,

could occur at high frequency between transgenic PREs [108] or between the transgenic PRE and the endogenous copy [109]. This suggests that Polycomb TAD interactions are an intrinsic feature and not a mere reflection of the linear disposition along the chromosome. Furthermore, the destabilization of these interactions has a direct effect on gene expression, demonstrating their functional relevance [66,109]. In terms of molecular components involved in this process, long-range interactions were shown to be partially dependent on PcG proteins [109] and on insulator components such as CTCF that binds to regulatory regions flanking the interacting PREs [57,110]. Depletion of CTCF affects long-range interactions between the *D. melanogaster* homeotic complexes, without affecting their local clustering [57], while EZH2 was found to have a similar role in mammals [111]. Surprisingly, mutations in several components of the RNAi pathway also reduce contact frequency [57,112], although the molecular role of these factors at PREs is not known. Finally, long-range Polycomb-dependent contacts occur in regions of high Polycomb concentration, called Polycomb foci [57,66,113–115], which can be seen as the physical manifestation of Polycomb TAD interactions. Noteworthy, PcG proteins and H3K27me3 mark do not affect TAD presence [4] and do not alter higher-order nuclear compartmentalization [94,116], but rather they define the chromatin state and the 3D organization of Polycomb-repressed TADs.

In summary, Polycomb-repressed TADs represent a compact chromatin environment with a complex internal multi-looped interaction network. As for the other TADs, internal contacts are highly privileged but inter-TAD contacts within the same chromosome arm form a higher-order network, driving Polycomb-repressed TADs into specific nuclear compartments [116], placing them apart from active chromatin and from lamina-associated chromatin.

Null Chromatin

Genome-wide mapping studies in *D. melanogaster* revealed that nearly half of the genome is covered by a highly repressive chromatin state that appears independent from the other well-known silencing systems (i.e., PcG and HP1) [17,23]. This “obscure” type of chromatin, originally baptized “black chromatin” or “null chromatin”, shows a lack of specific enrichments for the histone modifications tested [3,17,23]. The only proteins associated with this type of chromatin are shared with one or more different repressive chromatin types [23,117]. Among them, a strong enrichment is observed for lamin, which plays a central role for the silencing and the compartmentalization at nuclear periphery of null chromatin. This lamin-enriched chromatin type emerged also in similar studies in mammals, thus revealing a general

strategy to keep chromatin peripherally compartmentalized and transcriptionally silenced [16,18,20,21]. Something reminding null chromatin was found also in *C. elegans*, where a large portion of silenced genes was enriched in lamin and H3K9me1, H3K9me2 and H3K9me3 marks [22]. These findings suggest that, at least in some species, null chromatin displays some histone modifications. Moreover, it could be speculated that, in some organisms, null chromatin and classic heterochromatin might have been merged. High histone H1 presence in null chromatin [3,17,23] corroborates with gene expression data, as H1 has a negative effect on transcription and can induce chromatin compaction [118]. In *D. melanogaster*, null chromatin is organized in chromatin domains that are on average larger than the other types [17,23,119], showing a good overlap with TADs [3]. Therefore, “null TADs” might be most likely located at the nuclear periphery because of their high enrichment in lamins.

The nuclear periphery has been described to interact with transcriptionally inactive chromatin domains. However, some active genes in *metazoa* were also found to be associated to the nuclear pore proteins (Nups). These findings led to the idea that the nuclear pore could be a favorable environment for gene expression in metazoan nuclei, as it is in yeast. Remarkably, genes associated with Nups were found to be active in the nucleoplasm but silenced when tethered to the nuclear pore complexes in both *D. melanogaster* and human cells, suggesting that nuclear periphery is a quite homogeneously repressive environment in *metazoa* (reviewed in Ref. [120]). Besides nuclear pores, the internal surface of the nucleus is paved by the nuclear lamina, an intricate meshwork of proteins that physically separates the inner nuclear membrane from the peripheral chromatin. Its main components are lamins, which are intermediate filament proteins, and lamin-associated proteins [121]. A-type lamins are mostly expressed in differentiating cells whereas B-type lamins are expressed ubiquitously. Mutations in lamin genes lead to severe developmental defects in *D. melanogaster* [122] and in humans [123], including notably the Hutchinson-Gilford progeria syndrome [124].

LADs

The fragments of the genome interacting with the nuclear lamina are called lamin-associated domains or LADs. In *D. melanogaster*, LADs usually span from 7 to 700 kb, with a median size of 90 kb, bearing on average 7 genes per LAD [125]. Similarly, mammalian LADs are large and gene-poor domains spanning from 0.1 to 10 Mb, covering about 40% of the genome in a cell population [126,127]. About 500 genes were found to interact with lamin in flies. Interestingly, those genes had a very low transcriptional activity, lacking any active histone mark or heterochromatin mark. Moreover, they showed late

replication timing and had intergenic regions 7 times larger than average genes, none of these features alone being sufficient to predict lamin binding [128]. FISH experiments in *D. melanogaster* showed that LADs are located preferentially but not exclusively at the nuclear periphery, indicating a dynamic nature of lamin tethering [128]. Single cell studies conducted in mammals confirmed this trend, showing that only roughly one-third of the LADs are located at less than 1 μm from the nuclear lamina at any point in time. Interestingly, the fraction of the LADs that is associated with the periphery does not move toward the center of the nucleus during a given cell cycle [129]. The evolutionary conserved repressive nature of LADs is supported by genome-wide studies, showing that the average gene expression levels inside the LADs are consistently lower than outside [125–127]. Furthermore, tethering experiments of genes to the nuclear lamina corroborated the idea of a transcriptionally silenced compartment [130].

Genes clustered in LADs usually show developmental coregulation, as they can change simultaneously their expression together with their nuclear repositioning (Fig. 2a). For example, testis-specific genes in *D. melanogaster* tend to be organized in clusters and they are embedded in repressive nuclear peripheral compartments in somatic cells. These clusters are highly enriched for lamin and H1 but depleted for any active, heterochromatin or Polycomb-related marks. Upon depletion of lamin, somatic derepression of those genes is observed, together with detachment from the nuclear envelope [131]. Depletion of lamin can also cause misexpression of key developmental genes. For instance, the Hunchback gene moves to the nuclear periphery when the competence time window to specify early-born neurons is over. Depletion of lamin leads to detachment of hunchback gene from the nuclear periphery with concomitant reduction of its silencing and extension of the time window for neuroblast competence [132]. LADs display a dynamic behavior during development also in *C. elegans* [133] and in mammals [127], even though some LADs are more conserved than others among different cell types [134]. Their developmental reorganization can happen, as in *D. melanogaster*, at single gene level or at the level of entire LADs [127]. Null chromatin domains found in genome-wide association studies in mammals show strong overlap with LADs: they are organized in large domains and span a large portion of genome; they have the lowest transcriptional levels, have the lowest DNase I accessibility, have the highest lamina enrichments, lack any active mark [16,18,20], replicate late and have high levels of DNA methylation [21].

In *D. melanogaster*, chromatin regulation plays a key role in LAD dynamics. Depletion of lamin results in higher chromatin accessibility, as well as increased H3 and H4 acetylation. HDAC1 is required for

silencing, whereas HDAC3 has an auxiliary role in silencing but plays a key role in peripheral retention [135]. In a previous report, HDAC3 was found to interact at the nuclear periphery with LAP2 β , an integral nuclear-envelope protein with repressive function [136]. The role of HDAC3 in LAD peripheral maintenance is strikingly conserved from *D. melanogaster* to mammals [137–139]. Indeed, the lamin-associated protein Emerin binds HDAC3 at the nuclear periphery and activates its function [138]. Emerin depletion releases HDAC3 from the nuclear periphery [138] and correlates with loss of peripheral chromatin association [138,139]. Mammalian LADs also exhibit specific features, such as enrichment in G9a-dependent H3K9me2 [126,129] that is required for tethering to the lamina [129]. H3K9me2 was previously found to cover large portions of the genome, initially called “Locks” [140] that mostly reflect LADs [130]. This reinforces the idea that the so-called null chromatin is not devoid of all histone marks in every species. LADs are decorated with histone modifications also in other *metazoa*. Indeed, in *C. elegans* LADs, H3K9 is initially monomethylated and dimethylated by MET-25 and successively trimethylated by SET-25. H3K9me1/me2 modifications are required for the anchoring at the nuclear periphery and the H3K9me3 mark is responsible for transcriptional repression [141]. These results show that the anchoring and silencing mechanisms are coordinated but can be uncoupled. Moreover, the attachment to the nuclear periphery is not just a passive process driven by external forces but is at least partially driven by biochemical mechanisms. Mammalian LADs show very sharp borders, wherein the occupancy of lamin drops drastically within few kilobases. These borders are genetically defined, since they show the presence of bidirectional transcription units, usually pointing outward from LADs and bearing CpG islands and CTCF binding sites [126]. These features seem to be conserved in *D. melanogaster*, where very strong transcriptional units pointing outward and insulator proteins mark the sharp boundaries of null TADs [3,119] and LADs [125]. This active chromatin environment demarcating LAD borders may block the spreading of chromatin marks outside LADs. Strikingly, the same genetic determinants, that is, CTCF binding sites and highly expressed housekeeping genes, were found also at human and mouse TAD borders [5].

NADs

Nucleoli, besides rDNA arrays, also associate with actively transcribed RNA Pol III genes, with constitutive centromeric and telomeric heterochromatin and with nucleolar-associated domains or NADs [142]. NADs cover about 4% of the human genome, comprising loci with tissue-specific repression, transposable elements and repetitive sequences. There are several evidences

that NADs and LADs actually overlap. NADs can relocate at the nuclear periphery after cell division [143] and their linear size range highly corresponds with LADs. Moreover, a subset of internalized LADs was shown to become associated with the nucleolus [129]. Finally, tissue-specific repressed olfactory receptor genes, which were already shown to cluster to the nuclear periphery [144], were shown to also associate at the periphery of the nucleolus [142]. Thus, nuclear lamina and nucleolar periphery provide physical platforms to host null TADs.

In addition to null chromatin, the nuclear and the nucleolar peripheries can host constitutive heterochromatin [145]. Moreover, Polycomb-repressed chromatin shows a certain degree of lamin enrichment in genome-wide association studies [3,16,18,20,23]. Nevertheless, null chromatin is likely to represent the major flavor of chromatin to be localized both at the nuclear periphery and around nucleoli.

Constitutive Heterochromatin

Heterochromatin was originally defined as the chromatin portion that maintains high condensation during interphase [146] and was subdivided in facultative and constitutive heterochromatins [147]. Facultative heterochromatin corresponds to euchromatic regions that can become silenced and condensed under specific circumstances. In contrast, constitutive heterochromatin preserves its compaction regardless of the cellular context. In *metazoa*, constitutive heterochromatin usually comes in large blocks that are contiguous to centromeres and it is also called pericentric heterochromatin. Depending on the species, constitutive heterochromatin can also be found in other genomic regions. For example, in *D. melanogaster*, constitutive heterochromatin is located at pericentric regions, telomeres, most of the Y chromosome and on the small fourth chromosome [148]. The amount of constitutive heterochromatin is highly variable among different organisms: it covers about 30% of *D. melanogaster* and human genomes [149] and up to 90% in certain nematodes bearing holocentric chromosomes [150]. Constitutive heterochromatin is highly enriched in tandem repeats, satellite DNA and silenced transposable elements. It has very low rates of meiotic recombination and transcription besides replicating during late S phase. Gene density in constitutive heterochromatin is low compared to the rest of the genome, approximately 10-fold less in *D. melanogaster* [151]. These genes embedded in constitutive heterochromatin are actively transcribed and often essential for viability. Moreover, they require a heterochromatic environment to be expressed [149,152,153]. Besides RNA Pol II genes, both small and long noncoding RNAs are transcribed from heterochromatin [154–156], indicative of an environment not completely averse to transcription.

Universal hallmarks of constitutive heterochromatin are the presence of H4K20me₃, H3K9me₂/me₃ and HP1a (*heterochromatin protein 1a*), which binds to H3K9me₂/me₃ via its chromodomain [157]. H3K9me₂/me₃ marks are deposited in *D. melanogaster* pericentric heterochromatin by SU(VAR)3-9 and by its homologs in other species, but different heterochromatin environments can use different methyltransferases [148]. The borders between heterochromatin and euchromatin were initially described cytologically [158] and then by molecular approaches [159,160]. These borders are defined by sharp H3K9me₂ transitions and they show a substantial overlap among different tissues [153]. Euchromatic genes placed near those borders display a mosaic expression, namely, a variable transcriptional state in different cells. This phenomenon, initially discovered in *D. melanogaster*, (reviewed in Ref. [161]) and recently reported also in humans [162], was called PEV (*position effect variegation*) and was explained through a spreading model, predicting that the linear distance of a euchromatic gene from the heterochromatin border influences its transcriptional state. Interestingly, this model does not explain cases where a marker gene closer to heterochromatin is active and a more distant one is repressed. Thus, an alternative model has been proposed, confirming a linear polarity but introducing the possibility that chromatin loops could bring linear distant genes 3D closer to the nucleation sites. This 3D explanation can solve the observed skipping in the silencing of nearer genes [163].

Genome-wide studies recapitulated many of the already-known features of constitutive heterochromatin. In *D. melanogaster*, heterochromatin domains show enrichment for H3K9me₂/me₃ and for already-known heterochromatin proteins, together with other proteins shared with different chromatin types [3,17,23]. Average transcriptional activity is lower than in active chromatin but higher than Polycomb-repressed chromatin and null chromatin [23]. Moreover, high H1 enrichment [23] and the lowest density of DNase I hypersensitive sites [17] predict a very compact chromatin environment. Similar studies in humans confirmed the presence of H3K9me₃ domains enriched in repetitive sequences and devoid of active marks and H3K27me₃ [16,18–21].

Constitutive heterochromatin compaction

As mentioned above, constitutive heterochromatin represents by definition a highly condensed environment. Surprisingly, the first studies aimed to determine the relative levels of heterochromatin accessibility to DNA methylating enzymes [164] could not identify strong differences in accessibility compared to control regions, but similar approaches performed with transgenes with a well-characterized chromatin structure showed substantial differences in chromatin accessibility between euchromatic and

heterochromatic insertions. Transgenes inserted in several heterochromatic loci showed a reduction in accessibility to restriction enzyme digestion, together with transcriptional silencing. HP1a presence influenced both compaction and silencing of transgenes inserted into pericentric heterochromatic loci and in the fourth chromosome [165]. Reduced subtelomeric heterochromatin accessibility was further confirmed [166]. Moreover, micrococcal nuclease assays revealed a more regular nucleosomal ladder in heterochromatin compared to euchromatin, indicating a higher-order compaction with a constant repeat length [167].

The higher compaction observed in constitutive heterochromatin may not just depend on the lack of transcription since non-transcribed euchromatic genes maintain the same DNA accessibility when they become transcribed [85]. Interestingly, when the relative DNA accessibilities of euchromatin, constitutive heterochromatin and Polycomb-repressed chromatin were compared in the same study, the latter two showed similar low levels, regardless of their different molecular nature and genomic positions. These findings indicate that the two different compaction mechanisms may involve similar higher-order chromatin organization [85]. Finally, it is important to mention that transcription factors can, in some cases, challenge the heterochromatic environment and even be crucial for its establishment [168]. This means that DNA accessibility, although lower than in active regions, does not represent an insurmountable barrier for DNA-binding factors.

Long-range interactions and nuclear positioning of constitutive heterochromatin

There is no formal proof that constitutive heterochromatin is organized in TADs and technical difficulties in mappability given by the huge amount of repetitive sequences make it hard to answer this question. Nonetheless, either a TAD arrangement or an alternative 3D organization could be possible. In general, constitutive heterochromatin regions interact poorly with any other chromatin type, whereas they readily interact with other heterochromatin regions *in cis* and *in trans* [3].

In *D. melanogaster*, centromeres and pericentric heterochromatin coalesce into nuclear structures called chromocenters. In polytene salivary gland nuclei, there is a single chromocenter that clusters centromeres, the Y and fourth chromosomes in a single heterochromatic structure, located at the periphery of the nucleus. This cytological organization has been recapitulated by Hi-C studies performed in late *D. melanogaster* embryos [3] and cultured cells of embryonic origin [119]. Recently, clustering of *D. melanogaster* centromeres was shown to be dependent on CTCF and nucleoplasmin-like proteins. These proteins, together with the nucleolin homolog Modulo,

favor the interaction of centromeres with the periphery of the nucleolus [169]. In *D. melanogaster* embryos, heterochromatic telomeric sequences also cluster, but they cluster away from the chromocenter [3]. Mammalian nuclei display chromocenters in numbers and sizes that vary across species and cell types. For example, mouse chromocenters are more clustered than human counterparts [170]. Mammalian chromocenters reside at the nuclear periphery in late G1, then they disassemble and centromeres internalize in late S phase and G2. After mitosis, centromeres keep an internal position until early G1 [171,172]. Differentiation can either increase chromocenter clustering [170,172] or induce a de-clustering [173–175], according to the cell type.

Long-range interactions between heterochromatic foci and euchromatic genes can drive their silencing by a proximity effect. This phenomenon was called *trans*-inactivation in *D. melanogaster* [176]. The most famous example is the brown dominant allele (*bwD*), carrying a 1.6-Mb block of heterochromatic satellite sequence in its locus [177]. Whereas null alleles of *brown* are recessive, *bwD* can silence *in trans* the wild-type copy, dragging both alleles to pericentric heterochromatin [178]. The result is that the two alleles are repressed [176], even though the wild-type allele does not show the typical heterochromatic condensation or HP1a binding in polytene chromosomes [179]. Nevertheless, physical proximity to heterochromatin is not sufficient for silencing, since genes nearby *brown* do not get silenced and an active form of *brown* was found to be compatible with heterochromatin association [180]. Other examples of *trans*-inactivation were described in *D. melanogaster*, affecting protein coding genes [181,182] and transposable elements [183,184]. Similar long-range interactions between heterochromatin and silenced genes can also occur in mammals. For instance, in mouse thymocytes, specific loci are bound by the zinc-finger protein Ikaros and targeted to pericentric heterochromatin [185]. Ikaros firstly represses their transcription and then brings them to heterochromatin foci, where it multimerizes and physically bridges the repressed genes with the heterochromatin satellite repeats [186]. During the repositioning, deacetylation on H3K9ac occurs. After heterochromatic localization, firstly, there is demethylation of H3K4me3 and then methylation of H3K9, finally spreading bidirectionally and leading to an irreversible silencing [187]. Interestingly, genome-wide association studies in *D. melanogaster* have highlighted a special form of H3K9me2/me3 heterochromatin, not located at the classical genomic loci but rather embedded in euchromatin [17]. These ectopic heterochromatic domains vary among cell types and contain mostly silenced genes [17,153]. An intriguing hypothesis is that those tissue-specific silenced genes might be 3D tethered to pericentromeric heterochromatin, reflecting a looping mechanism.

Fig. 3. 3D representation of TADs. The active TAD1 in red, the Polycomb-repressed TAD2 and TAD3 in blue, the null TAD4 in black and the heterochromatic TAD 5 in green are depicted inside the cell nucleus. TAD1 harbors mostly active genes and is more decondensed and its nuclear positioning is more internal. TAD2 and TAD3 are more condensed than TAD1 and they are mainly transcriptionally silent. TAD4 is associated to the nuclear periphery and its genes are mostly silent. TAD5 is coated with constitutive heterochromatin. TAD5 not only has repressed transposable elements but also has few genes, which are expressed, regardless of the surrounding chromatin environment. The domains' borders harbor actively transcribed housekeeping genes.

In summary, constitutive heterochromatin represents a special chromatin environment, usually covering the centromeric and telomeric regions. Its condensation is fundamental for its functions and its compartmentalization radically shapes the genome architecture, also providing a potential platform for tissue specific gene silencing.

Conclusion

There is still much to understand about chromatin organization in *metazoa*, but some principles are beginning to emerge. TADs are the basic units of metazoan chromosomes and they represent a physical compartment for chromatin interactions. TADs are robust entities, since their borders are generally conserved among different cell types [4,5], even though they can shift in some instances [34,35]. Genetically defined TADs are associated with a particular chromatin type that dramatically alters TADs identity. The main chromatin types are basically four: active chromatin, Polycomb-repressed chromatin, null chromatin and constitutive heterochromatin, but further sub-classifications are possible and their description will help understand the complexity of the

system [3,20,21]. The chromatin type characterizing a TAD is switchable, giving a certain degree of freedom to these genomic entities (Fig. 2). This chromatin type confers to the TAD's some specific characteristics, which impact on TAD's functionality, even though a certain degree of internal heterogeneity is tolerated. The 3D organization of a TAD, adorned with a specific chromatin type, reflects its typical features as relative accessibility, chromatin compaction and looping contacts, which are characteristic of that particular chromatin environment. Despite these type-specific differences, the common feature of every TAD is its partial 3D separation from the rest of the genome (Fig. 3).

Moreover, the chromatin type of a TAD is a main factor for its nuclear positioning, favoring or disfavoring specific long-range contacts and driving it toward a preferential localization in the nucleus. The strong influence that chromatin types can give to TAD localization could be a major force in chromosome positioning and finally in genome architecture. For example, more gene-rich and transcriptionally active chromosomes occupy preferentially a more internal territory than gene-poor and silent ones do. Such a behavior at whole chromosome level may just reflect the tendencies of its own TADs, which finally could

drag the chromosome to different nuclear neighborhoods. Consequently, chromosomes with several null TADs could be more peripheral, as they will bind preferentially the nuclear lamina. This abundance of lamin binding TADs might lead to effective competition of inactive chromosomes against more active ones. Inactive chromosomes would thus locate at the periphery, at the expense of chromosomes carrying higher density of active TADs, which would place themselves in a more central position and would interact more easily with active TADs present on other chromosomes.

The chromatin type of TADs is switchable, and this change will influence its function together with its 3D internal organization. This feature should also affect nuclear architecture, as different cell types sharing their TADs but coated with different combination of chromatin types can have a completely different genome organization (Fig. 4). In this regard, it is important to mention that even two cells of the same type show a high variability in contacts between TADs [36], demonstrating that two cells displaying exactly the same nuclear organization do not exist. In summary, a given cell type, with a genome defined by the linear succession of different chromatin types, can have several possible 3D organizations. This is due to a certain degree of stochasticity and to the dynamics of the process. Nonetheless, two different cell types, displaying different chromatin landscapes, will have an even less similar nuclear organization.

The chromatin coating the genome has also been defined as the “epigenome”. This is due to the fact

that chromatin states, and particularly histone modifications, have been considered as potential carriers of epigenetic inheritance. In favor of this idea, many chromatin modifiers have been found on the replication forks, suggesting that the epigenome could be replicated along with the genome [188]. Remarkably, nucleosomes relocate after DNA replication. While duplicating chromatin, the parental histones are repositioned in a place that can be about 400 bp (corresponding to 2–3 nucleosomes) away from the original position [189]. In light of this fact, large domains of repressive marks (e.g., H3K27me3, H3K9me2, H3K9me3), rather than sharp peaks of active marks (e.g., H3K4me3, lysine acetylations), would represent better candidate for this epigenetic role. Since TAD's organization is completely lost during metaphase [190], a faithful epigenome replication would allow two daughter cells to have very similar chromatin landscapes, which may recapitulate a related genome organization. This principle, although partially true, cannot be universally applied. Indeed in mammals, LADs tethered to the nuclear periphery in the mother cell do not associate preferentially to the periphery in the daughter cell, meaning that there is no epigenetic mechanism to restore nuclear positioning. LAD association to the nuclear periphery is linked to a certain degree of stochasticity in the acquirement of dedicated histone marks, that is, H3K9me2, which finally drives the peripheral compartmentalization [129]. Older reports already showed that the same loci in daughter cells do not share the same nuclear positioning and therefore

Fig. 4. Impact of genetic features and chromatin type on the TAD. Fixed genetic elements define TAD borders, determining its length. The presence of genes and of functional elements inside a TAD are also genetically determined, as well as its genomic site. These features do not vary among different cell types. The chromatin type surrounding the TAD defines features as the DNA accessibility and the chromatin compaction. The chromatin environment can vary among different cell types and its partial replication will determine differences between different cells of the same type. Together, these genetic and epigenetic parameters will affect TAD 3D organization and nuclear positioning that will finally determine TAD function. The TAD tendency to occupy preferential nuclear positions will finally drive the global genome organization.

cannot be inherited from the mother cell [191]. The same principle can be applied to the conservation of chromosome territories, as their relative positions observed in daughter cells differ significantly from that of the mother cell. Apparently, chromosome territories are established in early G1 and stably maintained throughout the cell cycle, but during early prophase, a reshuffling occurs [182].

In conclusion, genome architecture relies on TAD organization. TADs are primarily defined by genetic determinants and further shaped by their chromatin environment. Epigenome replication processes will ensure the maintenance of their chromatin landscape and, consequently, of part of their 3D properties. Although the genome is faithfully replicated, the epigenome could be in part variable between two daughter cells. This variability, along with a high stochasticity in genome conformations, will lead to a partial conservation of genome architecture between two cells of the same type (Fig. 4).

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TAD, topologically associating domain; 3D, three-dimensional; PRE, Polycomb responsive element.

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